

MS25. Existing tools available for FAIRization identified and classified

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable aims at identifying a list of tools already available to help in the process to make/create FAIR data.

The list of tools presented and discussed come from a survey of several materials (on line document/ deliverables from other project / web resources/ recent papers).

Classification here proposed is based on several important aspects discussed in some detail in the introduction of this document.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
CAHIER	Corpus d'Auteurs pour les Humanités : Informatisation, Edition, Recherche
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
IFDS	Internet of FAIR Data and Services
IN	Implementation Network
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
VLRI	Very Large Research Infrastructure

Contents

1	Introduction: Identification and classification methodology	6
2	List of identified and classified tools	8
3	Conclusions.....	13

Executive summary

This deliverable aims at identifying a list of tools already available to help in the process to make/create FAIR data.

The list of tools presented and discussed come from a survey of several materials (on-line document/ deliverables from other project / web resources).

Classification here proposed is based on several important aspects discussed in the introduction of this document.

1 Introduction: Identification and classification methodology

In this introduction we briefly discuss the method we decided to adopt in the present document to firstly identify FAIRization tools available when this document is assembled and then to classify them.

It is useful, as a first step, to define the FAIRization process in order to better identify tools we are interested in. A simple possible definition, adapted from <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/fairification-process/>, where actually the process is identified as FAIRification, involves several steps:

- Original data retrieval
- Dataset identification and analysis
- Definition of the semantic model
- Data transformation
- License assignment
- Metadata definition
- FAIR Data resource deployment (data, metadata, license)

This process is still performed manually by most of data owner/producers and this limit its scalability and can be error prone and several differences/approaches can be generated. It is therefore important to have tools that automates as much as possible such process and make it stable and reproducible across different research communities.

In this milestone we tried, to the best of our knowledge, to identify which tools and technologies are currently available and which functionality in each step of the FAIRification process identified above. We also included in the analysis tools for FAIR Data management planning.

We explore several sources to identify tools available. We took into consideration: the following sources:

1.already published tools on the web, found by means of web searches and/or because referred within different documents.

An interesting starting point is this site, even if focused on life-science community: <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/research-data-management/data-management-knowledge-tools/>.

2.deliverables of active projects we are aware of.

3.online documents again identified and found by means of searches and/or because referred within different documents.

We then formulated a possible classification of tools by means of the following criteria:

1.easyness of use with respect to user community

2. Maturity level

3. Degree of adoptability with respect to different scientific communities

The outcome is then reported in the conclusion of this documents as a concise table where each single tool is classified according to the above criteria.

The most important resources used in the compilation of this milestone are here reported:

- <https://www.dtls.nl/fair-data/find-fair-data-tools/>
- <https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/Results%20Analysis%20of%20FAIR%20assessment%20tools%20v3.pdf>
- M. Thompson, K. Burger, R. Kaliyaperumal, M. Roos & L.O. Bonino da Silva Santos. Making FAIR easy with FAIR tools: From creolization to convergence. Data Intelligence 2(2020), 87–95. doi: 10.1162/dint_a_00031

2 List of identified and classified tools

This section reports the tools we identified and we considered of interest for our future work. For each of them we provide a short description, the source where we get this information and some more information to help us classifying them later. Classification parameters are then the ones reported in the introduction.

Name of the tool	Data Stewardship Wizard
Link	https://ds-wizard.org/about.html
Description	<p>Data Stewards capture and combine their knowledge and expertise with respect to the specific needs of a domain or an organisation. Researchers are truly guided through composing a DMP which can be then exported using selected template and format, including machine-actionable.</p> <p>The benefit lies not only in having a nowadays often obligatory DMP for funders but mainly learning how to handle data correctly, make them FAIR, maintain them well during the project, and curate them long-term.</p>
Additional Note	A starting point tool to help setup a correct data management plan
Which aspect ?	Data Management Plan
CLASSIFICATION parameter	1/2/3

Name of the tool	DMPONLINE
Link	doi 10.1007/978-3-642-15464-5_74.
Description	DMPOnline has recently seen rapid adoption from researchers and organizations as the go-to tool to produce funder-compliant DMPs. It provides an online, collaborative environment with (mostly) open text forms divided into sections following a configurable funder's DMP template. For each section, DMPOnline embeds explanatory text from a configurable set of sources, which may be DMP guidelines from funding organizations or academic institutions and may (or may not) contain FAIR-specific guidance.
Additional Note	It is not clear if the system is already available. At a first glance it seems not so friendly.
Which aspect ?	Data management Plan
CLASSIFICATION parameter	1/2/3

Name of the tool	Data FAIRport
Link	https://www.datafairport.org/
Description	The Data FAIRport is an interoperability platform that allows data owners to publish their (meta)data and allows data users to search for and access data (if licenses allow).

Additional Note	It Involves different tools touching different aspects of FAIR process. For more information please check the web page of the project.
Which aspect ?	All
CLASSIFICATION parameter	1/2/3

Name of the tool	OpenRefine
Link	http://openrefine.org/
Description	<p>OpenRefine is a powerful tool for working with messy data: cleaning it; transforming it from one format into another; and extending it with web services and external data.</p> <p>OpenRefine always keeps your data private on your own computer until YOU want to share or collaborate. Your private data never leaves your computer unless you want it to. (It works by running a small server on your computer and you use your web browser to interact with it)</p>
Additional Note	Born as a Google product, in October 2012, it was renamed OpenRefine as it transitioned to a community-supported product. It is indicated more for people which do not have programming skills.
Which aspect ?	Production of fair data

CLASSIFICATION parameter	1/2
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Name of the tool	FAIRifier
Link	
Description	This tools enables a post-hoc FAIRification workflow: load an existing data set (from a wide range of formats), (optionally) perform data wrangling tasks, add FAIR metadata) attributes to the data, generate a linked data version of the data and, finally, push the result to an online FAIR data infrastructure to make it accessible and discoverable
Additional Note	It is not clear the level of maturity: it is based on other tools and still in development. Not easy to use for non-experienced users.
Which aspect ?	Production of Fair Data but also aspects also involved
CLASSIFICATION parameter	1/2

Name of the tool	FAIR Data Point (FDP)
Link	https://github.com/FAIRDataTeam/FAIRDataPoint-Spec
Description	The FAIR Data Point's metadata layered approach is composed of five layers, namely, the FAIR Data Point itself, the collection of

	datasets, each one of the offered datasets, the datasets' distribution and the structure and semantics of each of dataset.
Additional Note	Not easy to be used for well-structured communities
Which aspect ?	Publishing FAIR data
CLASSIFICATION parameter	1/2/3

3 Conclusions

We searched among several sources to identify tools in order to provide an overview of what is available and avoid re-inventing the wheel in the activities within this task.

The following table summarize our survey; the list is, of course, partial: we just focused on a short list of tools we considered interesting for what we plan to do. We classified each tool using a simple 3 level scale (poor/fair/good).

This survey confirmed our idea that does not yet exist a mature ecosystem of tools, platforms and standards to support human and machine agents to manage, produce, publish and consume FAIR data in a user-friendly and efficient (i.e., “easy”) way.

Tool	Easiness of Use	Maturity level	Degree of adoptability	Notes
Data Stewardship Wizard	Good	Good	Good	
DPMONLINE	Unknown	Good	Good	
FAIRPort	Good	Fair	Good	
OpenRefine	Good	Good	Fair	
FAIRifier	Good	Fair	Fair	
FDP	Poor	Fair	Poor	